

Determinants of telepharmacy acceptance and medication adherence among hemodialysis patients (TEAM-HD): a cross-sectional study from Indonesia and Malaysia

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Abstract

The socioeconomic burden of end-stage kidney disease (ESKD) in Malaysia and Indonesia necessitates innovative care strategies. The TEAM-HD study assessed medication adherence and telepharmacy acceptance among hemodialysis patients in Selangor (Malaysia) and South Sulawesi (Indonesia). From April 2023 to April 2024, 131 patients (Malaysia: 71; Indonesia: 60), aged ≥ 18 years and undergoing long-term hemodialysis, completed a validated questionnaire on demographics, dialysis and medication-related factors, and telepharmacy acceptance. Acceptance of telepharmacy was moderate in both cohorts (Malaysia: 64.8%; Indonesia: 62.0%). In Malaysia, Chinese (adjusted odds ratio [aOR] 0.15) and Indian (aOR 0.18) patients were significantly less likely than Malays to accept telepharmacy. In Indonesia, younger age and higher household income were significantly associated with higher telepharmacy acceptance. High medication adherence was observed in both settings but was not associated with telepharmacy acceptance. These findings support implementing patient-centered, opt-in telepharmacy models and warrant cost-effectiveness evaluation in resource-constrained dialysis settings.

Keywords

hemodialysis, Malaysia and Indonesia, medication adherence, telepharmacy

Introduction

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is an epidemic in Southeast Asia (SEA), with an estimated 7.7% to 17.0% of individuals suffering from CKD stages 3 to 5 (Hustrini et al. 2024). The region is facing an exponentially rising burden of end-stage kidney disease (ESKD) cases, exacerbated by late diagnosis, limited CKD screening programs, and earlier disease onset in younger populations. In contrast, high-income countries have reported slower CKD progression and a lower prevalence of ESKD owing to earlier treatments, better access to nephrology care, and integrated disease management programs (Jadoul et al. 2024). Despite these global advancements, SEA continues to experience elevated rates of morbidity and mortality associated with kidney failure, underscoring the critical need for enhancements in long-term supportive care strategies (López et al. 2023).

Hemodialysis (HD) remains the predominant form of kidney replacement therapy, particularly in resource-intensive settings, where it is associated with a substantial socioeconomic burden (Bello et al. 2022). Patients undergoing HD face long-term challenges, including adherence to strict dietary restrictions, complex medication regimens, lifestyle modifications, and the logistical demands of frequent visits to dialysis centers. These realities demonstrate the importance of sustained and accessible patient education initiatives as part of standard HD care (Stevens et al. 2024).

In response, telemedicine has emerged as a promising model to improve access to kidney care, particularly in underserved or remote communities. In high-income settings, it has been integrated into nephrology services to facilitate proactive interventions in retarding disease progression, enhance monitoring of dialysis, and support symptom control, risk reduction, and patient training (Scherzer et al. 2025). Telepharmacy is an important subset of telemedicine that leverages telecommunication technologies to provide a wide range of pharmacy services, including medication therapy management, medication counseling and consultations, drug monitoring, and decision support (Alexander et al. 2017). Evidence from other chronic illness groups, such as those with diabetes and heart disease, shows that telepharmacy motivates patients to learn more about their illness, commit to long-term treatment, and experience optimal treatment outcomes (Cao et al. 2022). As noted by Kane-Gill and Rincon (2019), although telepharmacy is recognized as a useful strategy to expand pharmacist access, there is a significant lack of empirical data and best practice frameworks for telepharmacy in the context of CKD and dialysis care (Kane-Gill and Rincon 2019). This evidence gap calls for targeted investigations into telepharmacy's role in nephrology practice.

Although hemodialysis patients attend centers multiple times per week, on-site pharmacist services remain limited, particularly in independent or non-governmental organization (NGO)-run dialysis facilities (Dyer et al. 2022). Furthermore, patients often experience considerable physical and cognitive fatigue before and after dialysis sessions, making them less able to engage in educational

or counseling activities during treatment days (Dou et al. 2023). In this context, telepharmacy offers a practical, patient-centered solution that enables medication education and review to occur at more suitable times, when patients are more alert and receptive, such as on non-dialysis days in the comfort of their homes.

Malaysia (MY) and Indonesia (IND) are two neighboring SEA countries with comparable burdens of ESKD and growing interest in digital health solutions. Given that telepharmacy is in its early stages of development in both countries (Yen et al. 2022), there is a timely opportunity to explore its viability, acceptability, and potential impact on dialysis patients.

Materials and methods

An exploratory cross-sectional investigation was conducted using purposive sampling between 7 April 2023 and 7 April 2024. In MY, data collection took place at five non-governmental organization HD centers in Selangor State. Public hospital-based dialysis centers in Malaysia often feature pharmacist-led services such as Medication Therapy Adherence Clinics (MTAC). To ensure contextual alignment with Indonesia, where such structured pharmacist-led dialysis services are not yet routinely implemented, data collection in Malaysia was focused on NGO-run centers. This approach allowed for a more equitable comparison between settings where formal telepharmacy or structured pharmacy counseling services are either limited or absent, which more closely resembles the Indonesian care model. In IND, the study was conducted at HD centers in two district hospitals in South Sulawesi. Eligible patients were approached during routine dialysis sessions and invited to participate. Each patient received a Participant Information Sheet and was given adequate time to consider participation or seek clarification. A self-administered questionnaire was distributed upon obtaining written informed consent.

At study initiation, the estimated number of individuals aged 18 years and above receiving HD in MY and IND was approximately 1,775 and 1,317, respectively (13, 14). A minimum sample size of 60 respondents per country was calculated based on the standard formula for estimating proportions, using a 95% confidence interval and a 5% absolute margin of error. An assumed prevalence of 50% was applied to ensure a conservative estimate, in line with best practices for pilot studies (Viechtbauer et al. 2015). While the final sample accounts for approximately 3.5–4.5% of the total HD population in each country, it was deemed sufficient for exploratory analysis and hypothesis generation. Recruitment across multiple centers was employed to enhance the internal representativeness of each national cohort. Inclusion criteria were patients receiving HD who were able to communicate in English or the local language. Patients not prescribed any medications were excluded from the study.

Ethics approval was obtained from the ethics committees of Universiti Teknologi MARA (REC (PH)/UG/037/2023) and the University of Hasanuddin (705/UN4.6.4.5.31/PP36/2023).

Study instrument

The questionnaire was generated from a consensus of panel experts from both countries, consisting of three academicians, one renal pharmacist, one renal nurse, and one nephrologist. The expert panel validated 32 preliminary questions, of which 29 were selected, with a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.796, indicating good correlation. Forward and backward translation to the local language was conducted by two academicians from each country who were not involved in the generation of questions and were fluent in English and Bahasa Malaysia or English and Bahasa Indonesia. The translated questionnaire was piloted among 20 dialysis patients in each country to produce a validated, structured, and culturally oriented questionnaire for data collection.

Section A of the questionnaire contained nine questions focused on respondents' sociodemographic characteristics, whereas Section B contained three questions on medical and medication history. Section C, which assessed medication adherence, consisted of 17 questions grouped into five themes: importance of medication-taking (Questions 1–3), importance of obtaining medication information (Questions 4–6), difficulties in medication-taking (Questions 7–14), frequency of missed doses (Question 15), and interest in telepharmacy services (Questions 16–17). Question 15 was adapted from the End-Stage Renal Disease Adherence Questionnaire (ESRD-AQ), with permission from the American Nephrology Nurses Association (Kim et al. 2010). This item assessed medication adherence by asking, "During the past week, how often have you missed your prescribed medicines?" Adherence responses were scored on a categorical scale based on frequency of missed doses: 200 (none of the time), 150 (missed 1 day), 100 (missed 3–4 days), 50 (missed 5–6 days), and 0 (missed every day). The responses to Question 17, "If an online medication counseling service is available, I am interested to know more about it," were used to rate respondents' acceptance of telepharmacy service.

Data analysis

The anonymous web database was analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics software, version 29 (IBM Corporation, Armonk, NY, USA). Descriptive statistics summarized participants' sociodemographic characteristics, presented as frequencies, percentages, and means. The adherence level was categorized following Bloom's cut-off point, with a 'good adherence' score 200, a 'moderate adherence' score of 50, and a 'low adherence' scores of 0–100. The normality of data distribution was assessed using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test; due to the non-normal distribution of the adherence scores and the ordinal nature of the data, non-parametric statistics were employed.

The Mann–Whitney U test was used to compare adherence between the two countries. Furthermore, multivariate logistic regression was used to identify factors associated with good medication adherence and telepharmacy service acceptance. Variables were selected for inclusion in

the multivariate models based on a purposeful selection process: initially, all variables with a p-value < 0.25 in the univariate analysis were included to ensure a robust assessment of potential predictors. The data were not intended for inter-country comparison; rather, they were analyzed separately to understand the determinants within each country.

Results

Sociodemographic and dialysis-related factors

A total of 131 participants were recruited, with comparable representation from each country (MY: n = 71; IND: n = 60). The participants' sociodemographic characteristics are summarized in Table 1. Statistically significant differences were observed between the two cohorts across several variables, including education level, employment status, household income, number of medications, need for medication-related care, dialysis funding, duration on dialysis, and dialysis schedule.

Hypertension and diabetes mellitus were significantly more prevalent in the MY cohort compared to the IND group. The duration on hemodialysis was substantially longer among MY participants, with a mean duration of 24.0 months (SD = 53.1) compared to 10.4 months (SD = 22.0) in IND (p < 0.001).

Medication adherence

Overall, medication adherence was high among respondents, with Indonesian participants showing significantly higher adherence scores compared to Malaysian participants. The Mann–Whitney U test demonstrated a statistically significant difference in adherence between the two countries (U = 2553.50, z = 2.436, p = 0.015). This difference is illustrated in Fig. 1. Tables 2, 3 present the bivariate

Figure 1. Comparison of medication adherence scores between Malaysia (M) and Indonesia (I). Respondents from Indonesia (N = 60) demonstrated higher medication adherence than those from Malaysia (N = 71).

Table 1. Respondents' sociodemographic and dialysis-related characteristics by country (N = 131).

Description	Malaysia (n, %)	Indonesia (n, %)	All (N, %)	p-value
Number of participants	71	60	131	-
Sociodemographic characteristics				
Age (mean, SD)	54.5 (11.3)	50.2 (12.7)	52.6(12.1)	0.039 ^a
Gender				
Female	32(45.1)	32(53.3)	64(48.9)	0.346
Male	39(54.9)	28(46.7)	67(51.1)	
Ethnicity				
Malay	40(56.3)	-	40(56.3)	
Chinese	15(21.1)	-	15(21.1)	
Indian	16(22.5)	-	16(22.5)	<0.001
Makassar	-	36(60.0)	36(60.0)	
Betawi	-	1(1.7)	1(1.7)	
Bugis	-	22(36.7)	22(36.7)	
Marital status				
Married	62(87.3)	51(85.0)	113(86.3)	
Unmarried	9(12.7)	6(10.0)	15(11.5)	
Divorced	0(0)	3(5.0)	3(2.3)	
Education level				
No formal education	3(4.2)	2(3.3)	5(3.8)	
Primary education	9(12.7)	10(16.7)	19(14.5)	0.001
Secondary education	50(70.4)	23(38.3)	73(55.7)	
Tertiary education	9(12.7)	25(41.7)	34(26.0)	
Employment status				
Unemployed	48(67.6)	11(18.3)	79(60.3)	0.003
Government sector	3(4.2)	15(25.0)	18(13.7)	
Private sector	20(28.2)	14(23.3)	34(26.0)	
*Household income				
Low	62(87.3)	33(55.0)	95(72.5)	<0.001
Middle	6(8.5)	10(16.7)	16(12.2)	
High	3(4.2)	17(28.3)	20(15.3)	
Dialysis-related characteristics				
Number of medications				
1–3	3(4.2)	40(66.7)	43(32.8)	<0.001
4–7	43(60.6)	16(26.7)	59(45.0)	
8–11	14(19.7)	3(5.0)	17(13.0)	
12–15	6(8.5)	1(1.7)	7(5.3)	
>15	5(7.0)	0(0)	5(3.8)	
Medication care at home				
Independent	48(67.6)	7(11.7)	55(42.0)	<0.001
Dependent on family or caregiver	23(32.4)	53(88.3)	76(58.0)	
Dialysis funding				
Yes	53(74.6)	60(100.0)	113(86.3)	
No	18(25.4)	0(0)	18(13.7)	
Comorbidities				
No	7(9.9)	6(10.0)	13(9.9)	<0.001
Yes	64(90.1)	54(90.0)	118(90.1)	0.979
Hypertension	60(84.5)	41(68.3)	101(77.1)	0.028
Diabetes mellitus	42(59.2)	19(31.7)	61(46.6)	0.002
Cardiovascular	15(21.1)	7(11.7)	22(16.8)	0.149
Others	3(4.2)	6(10.0)	9(6.0)	0.193
Duration of dialysis (months)				
12 months or less	34(47.9)	39(65.0)	73(55.7)	
13–36 months	14(19.7)	13(21.7)	27(20.6)	
37–60 months	6(8.5)	5(8.3)	11(8.4)	
60 months or greater	17(23.9)	3(5.0)	20(15.3)	
Median (IQR)	24.0(53.1)	10.4(22.0)	12.0(31.4)	<0.001 ^a
How many days in a week do you receive hemodialysis?				
2 days or less	0(0)	34(56.7)	34(56.7)	<0.001
3 days	70(98.6)	26(43.3)	96(73.3)	
4 days	1(1.4)	0(0)	1(1.4)	

Description	Malaysia (n, %)	Indonesia (n, %)	All (N, %)	p-value
How many hours are you treated for each hemodialysis?				
less than 3 hours	0(0)	1(1.7)	1(1.7)	<0.001
3 hours	3(4.2)	2(3.3)	5(5.1)	
4 hours	68(95.8)	32(53.3)	100(76.3)	
More than 4 hours	0(0)	25(41.7)	25(41.7)	

aMann–Whitney U test RM, Ringgit Malaysia; Rp, Indonesian Rupiah.

*Income categories by national economic index: Low income (MY:<RM4,850; IDN:<Rp 2.500.000; Middle (MY: RM4,850–RM10,970; IDN: Rp 2.500.00–3.500.00; High income (MYR:> RM10,970; IDN: Rp > 3.500.00.

Table 2. Medication adherence rates to demographic and dialysis-related factors by country.

	Malaysia (n = 71)			Indonesia (n = 60)		
	Moderate adherence (n, %)	Good adherence (n, %)	p-value	Moderate adherence (n, %)	Good adherence	p-value
Total	8(11.3)	63(88.7)	-	5(8.3)	55(91.7)	-
Gender						
Male	8(100.0)	31(49.2)	0.007*	3(60.0)	25(45.5)	0.657*
Female	0(0)	32(50.8)		2(40.0)	30(54.5)	
Age, mean (SD)	47.6(14.8)	55.4(10.6)	0.066	49.6(9.6)	50.3(13.0)	0.909
Ethnicity						
Malay	34(54.0)	6(5.0)	0.528	-	-	
Chinese	14(22.2)	1(12.5)		-	-	
Indian	15(23.8)	1(12.5)		-	-	
Makassar	-	-		4(80.0)	32(59.3)	0.653
Betawi	-	-		0(0)	1(1.9)	
Bugis	-	-		1(20.0)	21(38.9)	
Marital status						
Married	6(75.0)	56(88.9)	0.266*	4(80.0)	47(85.5)	0.570*
Unmarried	2(25.0)	7(11.1)		1(20.0)	8(14.5)	
Education level						
Primary and less education	1(12.5)	11(17.5)	0.532	1(20.0)	11(20.0)	0.527
Secondary education	5(62.5)	45(71.4)		3(60.0)	20(36.4)	
Tertiary education	2(25.0)	7(11.1)		1(20.0)	24(43.6)	
Employment status						
Unemployed	4(50.0)	44(69.8)	0.423*	3(60.0)	28(50.9)	1.000*
Employed	4(50.0)	19(30.2)		2(40.0)	27(49.1)	
***Household income						
Low	6(75.0)	56(88.9)	0.408	30(54.5)	3(60.0)	
Middle	1(12.5)	5(7.9)		10(18.2)	0(0.0)	0.55
High	1(12.5)	2(3.2)		15(27.3)	2(40.0)	
Number of medications						
1–3	0(0)	3(4.8)	0.278	4(80.0)	36(65.5)	
4–7	4(50.0)	39(61.9)		0(0)	16(29.1)	
8–11	1(12.5)	13(20.6)		0(0)	3(5.5)	0.005
12–15	1(12.5)	5(7.9)		1(20.0)	0(0)	
>15	2(25.0)	3(4.8)		0(0)	0(0)	
Medication care at home						
Dependent on family or caregiver	2(25.0)	21(33.3)	1.000*	48(87.3)	5(100)	1
Independent	6(75.0)	42(66.7)		7(12.7)	0(0)	
Dialysis funding						
Yes	6(75.0)	47(74.6)	1.000*	5(100.0)	55(100.0)	-
No	2(25.0)	16(25.4)		0(0)	0(0)	
Comorbidities						
Hypertension	7(87.5)	53(84.1)	1.000*	0(0)	41(74.5)	0.002*
Diabetes mellitus	4(50.0)	38(60.3)	0.708*	1(20.0)	18(32.7)	1.000*
Cardiovascular	2(25.0)	13(20.6)	0.673*	2(40.0)	5(9.1)	0.099*
Others	1(12.5)	2(3.2)	0.305*	1(20.0)	5(9.1)	0.421*
Duration of dialysis (months)						
12 months or less	6(75.0)	28(44.4)	0.256	3(60.0)	36(65.5)	
13–36 months	1(12.5)	13(20.6)		1(20.0)	12(21.8)	0.9
37 months and more	1(12.5)	22(34.9)		1(20.0)	7(12.7)	
Median (IQR)	11.0(17.1)	36.0(75.0)	0.139**	7.9(31.3)	12.0(22.0)	0.897**

	Malaysia (n = 71)			Indonesia (n = 60)		
	Moderate adherence (n, %)	Good adherence (n, %)	p-value	Moderate adherence (n, %)	Good adherence	p-value
How many days in a week do you receive hemodialysis?						
2 days or less	-	-		3(60.0)	31(56.7)	1.000*
3 days	8(100.0)	62(98.4)	1.000*	2(40.0)	24(43.6)	
4 days	0(0)	1(1.6)		-	-	
How many hours are you treated for each hemodialysis?						
Less than 3 hours	-	-		-	-	
3 hours	1(12.5)	2(3.2)	0.305*	1(20.0)	2(3.6)	0.211
4 hours	7(87.5)	61(96.8)		3(60.0)	29(52.7)	
More than 4 hours	-	-		1(20.0)	24(43.6)	

*Fisher's exact test;

**Mann-Whitney U test;

Adherence levels (score): Good (200), Moderate (150), Low (0–100);

***Income categories by national economic index: Low income (MY:<RM4,850; IDN:<Rp 2.500.000;

Middle (MY: RM4,850–RM10,970; IDN: Rp 2.500.00–3.500.00 High income (MYR:> RM10,970; IDN: Rp > 3.500.00.

Table 3. Multivariate logistic regression for the likelihood of good medication adherence by country.

Characteristics	p-value	OR	95% CI for OR	
			Upper	Lower
Malaysia				
Age, yrs, mean (SD)	0.103	1.058	0.989	1.131
Household income				
Low (ref.)				
Middle	0.367	0.316	0.026	3.849
High	0.211	0.172	0.011	2.708
Duration of dialysis (months)				
12 months or less				
13–36 months	0.719	1.543	0.146	16.347
37 months and more	0.199	4.465	0.454	43.9
INDONESIA				
Number of medications				
7 and less (ref.)				
8 and more	0.32	0.254	0.017	
Comorbidities				
Diabetes Mellitus				
Hypertension				
Cardiac disease	0.276	0.271	0.026	2.847
Other diseases				
Duration of hemodialysis treatment				
4 hours (ref.)				
< 4 hours	0.479	0.326	0.015	7.251
> 4 hours	0.622	1.838	0.164	20.619

MY—variables with p-value < 0.25 from univariate analysis. Hosmer and Lemeshow test; $\chi^2(8) = 7.105$, $p = 0.525$, indicating a good fit of the model to the data.

IND—variables with p-value < 0.25 from univariate analysis. Hosmer and Lemeshow test; $\chi^2(2) = 0.353$, $p = 0.838$, indicating a good fit of the model to the data;

CI: confidence interval, MY: Malaysia, IND: Indonesia, OR: odds ratio.

and multivariate analyses of factors associated with medication adherence in Malaysia and Indonesia. Among Malaysian participants (n = 71), 88.7% demonstrated good medication adherence. Bivariate analysis revealed a significant association between gender and adherence, with all participants reporting moderate adherence being male ($p = 0.007$). Although other variables were not statistically significant, a trend was observed whereby patients with longer hemodialysis duration appeared more likely to report good adherence. In particular, durations ≥ 37 months were associated with higher odds of adherence (OR 4.47; 95% CI: 0.45–43.90; $p = 0.199$), though this association did not reach statistical significance. In the Indonesian

cohort (n = 60), 91.7% of participants demonstrated good adherence. Bivariate analyses showed that hypertension ($p = 0.002$) and fewer prescribed medications ($p = 0.005$) were significantly associated with better adherence. In multivariate analysis, no variables remained statistically significant; however, lower pill burden continued to show a suggestive association with improved adherence (OR 0.25; $p = 0.320$).

Although overall adherence was high in both settings, the associated factors differed. In Malaysia, gender and longer dialysis duration may play a role, while in Indonesia, hypertension and polypharmacy appear more influential. Further details of univariate analyses for both countries are provided in Suppl. material 1: table S1.

Telepharmacy acceptance

Among Malaysian participants (n = 71), 64.8% reported acceptance of telepharmacy services. Bivariate analysis (Table 4) showed that ethnicity and dialysis funding status were significantly associated with acceptance. Specifically, Malay participants were significantly more likely to accept telepharmacy compared to Chinese and Indian ethnic groups ($p = 0.002$). Similarly, those receiving subsidized dialysis were more likely to report acceptance than those without financial assistance (84.8% vs. 15.2%, $p = 0.011$). No significant associations were observed for gender, age, education level, employment, or dialysis-related variables. Multivariate logistic regression (Table 5) confirmed ethnicity as an independent predictor of telepharmacy acceptance. Compared to Malays, Chinese (aOR 0.15, 95% CI: 0.04–0.62; $p = 0.009$) and Indian (aOR 0.18, 95% CI: 0.05–0.68; $p = 0.012$) participants were significantly less likely to accept telepharmacy. While dialysis funding showed a positive association with acceptance (aOR 3.28, 95% CI: 0.90–11.99; $p = 0.073$), this did not reach statistical significance. The model fit calibration was adequate (Hosmer–Lemeshow $\chi^2 = 1.6$, $p = 0.952$).

In Indonesia (n = 60), 62.0% of respondents expressed acceptance of telepharmacy. Bivariate analysis identified younger age ($p < 0.001$) and higher household income ($p = 0.049$) as significant factors. No significant associations were found for gender, education, comorbidities,

Table 4. Telepharmacy acceptance rates to demographic and clinical characteristics by country.

Characteristic	Malaysia (n = 71)			Indonesia (n = 60)		
	No (n, %)	Yes (n, %)	p-value	No (n, %)	Yes (n, %)	p-value
Total	25(35.2)	46(64.8)	-	22(38.0)	36(62.0)	-
Gender						
Male	11(44.0)	28(60.9)	0.172	11(50.0)	16(44.4)	0.681
Female	14(56.0)	18(39.1)		11(50.0)	20(55.6)	
Age, mean (SD)	57.2(10.9)	53.1(11.3)	0.112**	57.9(8.7)	45.5(12.9)	<0.001
Ethnicity						
Malay	7(28.0)	33(71.7)	0.002	-	-	
Chinese	9(36.0)	6(13.0)		-	-	
Indian	9(36.0)	7(15.2)		-	-	
Makassar	-	-		14(63.6)	21(60.0)	
Betawi	-	-		1(4.5)	0(0)	
Bugis	-	-		7(31.8)	14(40.0)	
Marital status						
Married	23(92.0)	39(84.8)	0.478*	18(81.8)	31(86.1)	0.718*
Unmarried	2(8.0)	7(15.2)		4(18.2)	5(13.9)	
Education level						
Primary and less education	7(28.0)	5(10.9)	0.180*	6(27.3)	4(11.1)	0.245*
Secondary education	15(60.0)	35(76.1)		7(31.8)	16(44.4)	
Tertiary education	3(12.0)	6(13.0)		9(40.9)	16(44.4)	
Employment status						
Unemployed	17(68.0)	31(67.4)	1	10(45.5)	16(44.4)	0.589
Employed	8(32.0)	15(32.6)		12(54.5)	20(55.6)	
***Household income						
Low	22(88.0)	40(87.0)	1.000*	11(50.0)	20(55.6)	0.049*
Middle	2(8.0)	4(8.7)		7(31.8)	3(8.3)	
High	1(4.0)	2(4.3)		4(18.2)	13(36.1)	
Number of medications						
1–3	2(8.0)	1(2.2)	0.413*	15(68.2)	25(69.4)	
4–7	14(56.0)	29(63.0)		6(27.3)	9(25.0)	
8–11	7(28.0)	7(15.2)		1(4.5)	2(5.6)	1.000*
12–15	1(4.0)	5(10.9)				
>15	1(4.0)	4(8.7)				
Medication care at home						
Dependent on family or caregiver	9(36.0)	14(30.4)	0.791	20(90.9)	31(86.1)	0.698*
Independent	16(64.0)	32(69.6)		2(9.1)	5(13.9)	
Dialysis funding						
Yes	14(56.0)	39(84.8)	0.011	22(100.0)	36(100.0)	-
No	11(44.0)	7(15.2)		0(0)	0(0)	
Comorbidities						
Hypertension	20(80.0)	40(87.0)	0.501	15(68.2)	26(72.2)	0.773
Diabetes mellitus	13(52.0)	29(63.0)	0.451	8(36.4)	11(30.6)	0.775
Cardiovascular	5(20.0)	10(21.7)	1	2(9.1)	5(13.9)	0.698*
Others	0(0)	3(6.5)	0.547*	2(9.1)	3(8.3)	1.000*
Duration of dialysis (months)						
12 months or less	10(40.0)	24(52.2)	0.397*	11(50.0)	26(72.2)	0.233*
13–36 months	7(28.0)	7(15.2)		7(31.8)	6(16.7)	
37 months and more	8(32.0)	15(32.6)		4(18.2)	4(11.1)	
Median (IQR)	36.0(67.0)	12.0(56.8)	0.894**	15.0(33.3)	9.9(20.5)	0.33
How many days in a week do you receive hemodialysis?						
2 days or less				12(54.5)	22(61.1)	0.784
3 days	25(100.0)	45(97.8)	1	10(45.5)	14(38.9)	
4 days	0(0)	1(2.2)		-	-	
How many hours are you treated for each hemodialysis?						
Less than 3 hours	-	-		-	-	
3 hours	0(0)	3(6.5)	0.547*	1(4.5)	2(5.6)	
4 hours	25(100.0)	43(93.5)		11(50.0)	19(52.8)	1.000*
More than 4 hours	-	-		10(45.5)	15(41.7)	

*Fisher's exact test;

**Mann-Whitney U test;

***Income categories by national economic index: Low income (MY:<RM4,850; IDN:<Rp 2.500.000, Middle (MY: RM4,850–RM10,970; IDN: Rp 2.500.00–3.500.00; High income (MYR:> RM10,970; IDN: Rp > 3.500.00).

Table 5. Multivariate logistic regression for the likelihood of telepharmacy acceptance by country.

Characteristics	Model 1			
	p-value	aOR	95% CI	
Malaysia				
Ethnicity				
Malay (ref.)				
Chinese	0.009	0.152	0.037	0.622
Indian	0.012	0.175	0.045	0.677
Education level				
Secondary education (ref.)				
Primary and less education	0.169	0.35	0.078	1.561
Tertiary education	0.563	0.601	0.107	3.374
Dialysis funding	0.073	3.276	0.895	11.989
INDONESIA				
Age, yrs, mean (SD)	0.007	0.901	0.835	0.973
Education level				
Secondary education (ref.)				
Primary and less education	0.077	0.185	0.028	1.203
Tertiary education	0.65	0.632	0.087	4.598
Household income				
Low (ref.)				
Middle	0.059	0.13	0.016	1.085
High	0.872	1.159	0.193	6.956
Duration of dialysis (months)				
12 months or less (ref.)				
13–36 months	0.153	0.254	0.039	1.661
37 months and more	0.878	0.857	0.121	6.096

MY—variables with p-value < 0.05 from univariate analysis. Hosmer and Lemeshow test, $\chi^2(6) = 1.6$, $p = 0.952$, indicating a good fit of the model to the data.

IND—variables with p-value < 0.25 from univariate analysis. Hosmer and Lemeshow test, $\chi^2(7) = 6.3$, $p = 0.509$, indicating a good fit of the model to the data.

CI: confidence interval, MY: Malaysia, IND: Indonesia, OR: odds ratio.

or dialysis characteristics. In multivariate analysis, age remained a significant predictor, with each additional year associated with a 10% decrease in the odds of acceptance (aOR 0.90 per year increase, 95% CI: 0.84–0.97; $p = 0.007$). Trends toward higher acceptance were observed among those with greater income and education, though these were not statistically significant. Model fit was acceptable (Hosmer–Lemeshow $\chi^2 = 6.3$, $p = 0.509$).

Overall, telepharmacy acceptance was comparable between Malaysia and Indonesia, at approximately 62–65%. However, the influencing factors differed: in Malaysia, acceptance was associated with ethnicity and dialysis funding, while in Indonesia, it was influenced by age and income level. Suppl. material 1: table S2 details the univariate analysis of factors affecting telepharmacy acceptance in both countries. Full univariate results are presented in Suppl. material 1: table S2.

Discussion

This study examines the determinants of telepharmacy acceptance and medication adherence among hemodialysis patients in Malaysia and Indonesia, offering comparative insights grounded in local health system realities. While adherence to medication and the acceptance rates of telepharmacy services were notably high in both countries, the patterns of influence differ based on healthcare infrastructure,

individual characteristics, and perceived support systems. These findings offer regionally relevant evidence to inform the design and implementation of patient-centered digital health strategies in dialysis care across Southeast Asia.

Medication adherence and treatment complexity

Our findings revealed trends of better adherence among female patients and those with longer dialysis vintage in Malaysia. Gender differences in adherence have been linked to social roles, employment obligations, and psychological factors (Ozen et al. 2019). A qualitative study in local dialysis settings reported that many women frame taking medicines as a self-trust to stay well for their family and to fulfil religious obligations, such as caring for children and being able to fast safely (Woei et al. 2024). Another Malaysian study has similarly reported higher engagement among female patients in pharmacist-led clinics and better compliance with dialysis restrictions on fluid, diet, and medicines (Lee and Chong 2022). The inclination for better adherence among dialysis veterans suggests a combination of experiential learning and a survivor effect, in which patients who remain in treatment long enough accumulate knowledge, embed routines, and are more likely to persevere (Lim et al. 2020). These findings support targeted adherence strategies, while also prioritizing new hemodialysis patients for structured medication education. Peer-support models, such as buddy systems linking new and experienced patients, may also be beneficial.

In the Indonesian cohort, patients who were prescribed fewer medications exhibited better adherence. While polypharmacy is a well-established barrier to adherence, this finding aligns with national data highlighting treatment complexity as a critical challenge in multimorbidity management. Two plausible explanations for this trend are (a) access to dialysis medications and (b) cultural interpretations of pill burden. Indonesia's National Health Insurance scheme (i.e., Badan Penyelenggara Jaminan Sosial Kesehatan, BPJS Kesehatan scheme) provides broad coverage for basic health necessities but does not fully subsidize all prescribed medications. Consequently, lower pill burdens seen in our study may reflect nonintentional non-adherence driven by efforts to reduce out-of-pocket expenses. Furthermore, cultural reliance on traditional remedies, such as 'jamu,' may be intensified when prescribed medications are perceived as expensive or unaffordable. National surveys indicate that the use of traditional herbal remedies increased from 63.8% to 71.5% between 2016 and 2019, with even higher usage among those with underlying chronic diseases (Utomo et al. 2022; Pradipta et al. 2025). Regimen simplification, such as once-daily dosing, clear labeling of medication, and increasing public education campaigns addressing the risks of unregulated traditional remedies in kidney disease, may be beneficial.

Telepharmacy and dialysis care realities

The overall acceptance of telepharmacy in this study is modest, at 62.0% in Malaysia and 64.0% in Indonesia, which is consistent with findings from other upper-middle-income

countries, such as Vietnam (60.3%) and Jordan (61.3%) (Abu-Farha et al. 2023; Dat et al. 2024). This pattern suggests a stable baseline of receptiveness to telepharmacy in settings where digital health infrastructure is still maturing. Conversely, research conducted in India and Singapore, where patients had prior exposure to telepharmacy or telenephrology services, revealed higher acceptance rates, ranging from 74% to 90% (George et al. 2022; Yan et al. 2022). These comparisons support the proposition that familiarity and repeated use enhance patient confidence and uptake. Collectively, this evidence suggests that while initial acceptance may be moderate among first-time users, controlled exposure, perceived convenience, and alignment with treatment workflows, such as reduced travel burden in hemodialysis, can meaningfully increase engagement. In the Malaysian cohort, acceptability was significantly greater among Malay respondents and those receiving subsidized dialysis. This observation reflects structural enablers, such as language-aligned education, rather than cultural predispositions. Malay communities are more inclined to rely on medical treatments from public or semi-public facilities (Ismail et al. 2023) and are thus more familiar with pharmacist-led counseling programs. Consequently, introducing telepharmacy via resources in Bahasa Malaysia in this study may have enhanced engagement and comfort for this group compared to other groups. Expanding access to materials in Mandarin and Tamil, the two other most spoken languages locally, may further improve inclusivity.

Malaysia's universal healthcare system subsidizes dialysis treatment through various public, commercial, and non-governmental funds, including the Ministry of Health (MOH), the Social Security Organisation (SOCSSO), and welfare programs (Ismail et al. 2019; Ong et al. 2022). Patients benefiting from these subsidies are also more likely to have prior exposure to structured pharmacist counseling in public healthcare settings, which may foster greater familiarity with pharmacist-led services and lead them to perceive telepharmacy as a valuable extension of care. Nonetheless, financial difficulties may continue to affect certain patients who are in the process of applying for funding, which may influence their willingness to participate in additional services. Together, these factors appear to shape acceptance, with important implications for expanding telepharmacy across both public and private dialysis settings.

In the Indonesian cohort, telepharmacy acceptance was significantly higher among younger patients and those with higher incomes. These patterns likely reflect digital readiness, financial access, and attitudes toward self-care. Younger patients tend to be more comfortable using smartphones, health applications, and online platforms, as supported by national trends showing high digital engagement among adults under 40 years (APJII 2023). Meanwhile, patients with higher incomes are more likely to hold contributory BPJS insurance, afford stable mobile data, and possess the health literacy necessary to navigate remote services independently (Pradipta et al. 2024; Pradipta et al. 2025). Collectively, these factors suggest that digital access, self-efficacy, and socioeconomic resources significantly shape telepharmacy acceptance in Indonesia.

Implication to practice

The results of this study suggest that telepharmacy can function as an efficient and scalable approach to enhance medication education and adherence among hemodialysis patients, especially in environments with limited access to pharmacists. To improve acceptance, factors that are locally and culturally rooted should be carefully considered during the introduction of such services. These include the implementation of telepharmacy in publicly accessible facilities, embedding it within patients' care pathways, and the use of languages or dialects that patients are comfortable with to encourage meaningful communication. These features can be effectively adapted for use in dialysis centers operating within hospitals or independently outside hospital settings. For wider adoption, telepharmacy should use an opt-in approach tailored to patient needs, with flexible scheduling, affordable access, and alignment with long-term care. Capacity building through standardized patient education modules and subsidized platforms can support its expansion. Future research should assess cost-effectiveness and delivery models suited for resource-limited settings. Policy should ensure equitable access to pharmacist-led support across all dialysis providers.

Strengths and limitations

This study is the first to examine both medication adherence and telepharmacy acceptance among dialysis patients in Indonesia and Malaysia, offering data to guide region-specific and cross-border strategies. The use of a validated instrument minimized variability across cultural and systemic differences. The analysis provides a multidimensional view of sociodemographic, funding, and medication-related factors, alongside the evolving burden of ESKD among younger populations. Nonetheless, methodological limitations include potential selection bias from convenience sampling and information bias from self-reporting. The absence of data on technological access, literacy, and readiness limits the scope of telepharmacy applicability. Future research should address these limitations, including direct evaluation of digital barriers, willingness to pay for services, and longitudinal designs to track adherence trends and telepharmacy utility across diverse patient profiles.

Conclusion

Improving access to telepharmacy is not merely a digital convenience; it is a strategic means of strengthening medication adherence. Telepharmacy offers a patient-centered solution by reducing barriers such as travel fatigue, limited health literacy, and unnecessary clinic visits, while enhancing the consistency, understanding, and motivation needed for long-term adherence. Expanding telepharmacy across all dialysis settings, particularly those currently underserved, has the potential to close the adherence gap, improve clinical outcomes, and promote a more equitable model of care for the growing dialysis population.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Indonesia: University Hasanuddin Ethics Committee (705/UN4.6.4.5.31/PP36/2023) Malaysia: Faculty Ethics Review Committee (FERC) of University Teknologi Mara Malaysia (UiTM) (REC (PH)/UG/037/2023).

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT and QuillBot Premium only to enhance sentence structure and refine the English language. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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Author contributions

A. Anggriani: Conceptualization, Writing, Methodology, Resources, Writing – Original Draft, Supervision, Project Administration, Funding Acquisition. Norkasih Ibrahim: Conceptualization, Validation, Formal Analysis, Writing – Review & Editing, Project Administration. Yulia Yusrini Djibir: Validation, Writing – Review & Editing. Muh. Akbar Bahar: Validation, Writing – Original Draft. Ahmad Fauzi Dali: Methodology, Resources, Writing – Original Draft, Supervision. Siti Nur Aisyah: Investigation, Writing – Original Draft. Alfani Muthi'ah Mustafaina Kamil: Investigation, Writing – Original Draft. Astrid Ananda: Investigation, Writing – Original Draft. Graciella Valencia Ambakaraeng: Investigation, Writing – Original Draft. Yogini Jani: Conceptualization, Writing – Review & Editing. Muhammad Iqbal Abdul Hafidz: Methodology – Review & Editing.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Univariate analysis for the likelihood of good medication adherence and telepharmacy acceptance for Malaysia (MY) and Indonesia (IND)

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